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MODULATION OF GLICLAZIDE PERMEABILITY BY PROBIOTIC BACTERIA AND BILE ACIDS: INSIGHTS FROM THE PAMPA MODEL

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Introduction: Gut microbiota and bile acids can modify drug metabolism, solubility, and permeability, which may significantly affect therapeutic efficacy. Given the variable clinical response of gliclazide, understanding the influence of these factors is crucial. This study examines the effects of probiotic bacteria and bile acids on gliclazide permeability.

Material & Methods: Gliclazide permeability was assessed using the in vitro PAMPA model, with and without probiotic bacteria and bile acids (cholic acid, CA; deoxycholic acid, DCA) at pH 5.8, 6.5, and 7.4. Drug concentrations were determined by HPLC, and molecular mechanics (MM2) calculations were used to evaluate interactions between gliclazide and bile acids.

Results: Probiotic bacteria significantly increased gliclazide permeability across the PAMPA membrane at all pH values. At pH 7.4, a reduction in gliclazide concentration was observed, suggesting potential bacterial metabolism or drug bioaccumulation in bacteria. In contrast, bile acids decreased gliclazide permeability, with DCA showing a stronger effect than CA, likely due to the formation of stable complexes, as confirmed by MM2 calculations.

Conclusion: These findings suggest that gut microbiota and bile acids modulate gliclazide permeability, which could affect its bioavailability. Further in vivo studies are required to explore the impact of these interactions on gliclazide efficacy.

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References

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